

**МІНІСТЕРСТВО ОСВІТИ І НАУКИ УКРАЇНИ
СУМСЬКИЙ НАЦІОНАЛЬНИЙ АГРАРНИЙ УНІВЕРСИТЕТ**

**DIGITAL ETIQUETTE:
PRINCIPLES OF SPEAKING
AND BEHAVIOUR**

**Методичні вказівки щодо
проведення практичних занять**

СУМИ – 2023

**МІНІСТЕРСТВО ОСВІТИ І НАУКИ УКРАЇНИ
СУМСЬКИЙ НАЦІОНАЛЬНИЙ АГРАРНИЙ УНІВЕРСИТЕТ**

**Біолого-технологічний факультет
Кафедра іноземних мов**

**DIGITAL ETIQUETTE:
PRINCIPLES OF SPEAKING
AND BEHAVIOUR**

**Методичні вказівки щодо
проведення практичних занять**

**для викладачів навчального курсу
“Major EU practices on media literacy
for boosting students’ critical thinking
in the frame of the target language learning”**

СУМИ – 2023

УДК 378.1:174.4+395(072)

ББК 87.75я73

Укладач: Фоменко Т.М., доцентка, канд. пед. наук, доцентка кафедри іноземних мов СНАУ

Digital etiquette: principles of speaking and behaviour. Методичні вказівки щодо проведення практичних занять. Суми: СНАУ, 2023 р. 35 с. 1,5 др.арк.

Методичні рекомендації розроблені для викладачів іноземних мов щодо формування знань студентів із цифрового етикету під час вивчення навчального курсу “Major EU practices on media literacy for boosting students’ critical thinking in the frame of the target language learning”, що реалізується в межах проєкту Еразмус+ Модуль Жана Моне “EU strategies extrapolation for boosting students’ media literacy in Ukrainian HE”.

Методична розробка складена відповідно до програми навчального курсу за темами “Media literacy in the context of communication and collaboration” і “Safety in media space and the basics of cyber security”.

Методичні рекомендації містять план практичних занять і список літератури до них. У роботі також репрезентовано методичні поради, питання для обговорення, різноманітні практичні завдання з формування цифрового етикету та правила поведінки під час дистанційного та онлайн навчання.

Рецензенти:

Литвинко О.А., доцентка, канд. філол. наук, доцентка кафедри іноземних мов СНАУ

Білоцерковець М.А., доцентка, канд. пед. наук, доцентка кафедри іноземних мов СНАУ

Відповідальний за випуск:

Бересток О.В., ст. викладачка кафедри іноземних мов СНАУ

Рекомендовано до видання навчально-методичною радою біолого-технологічного факультету.

Протокол № 7 від «14» квітня 2023 року.

© Сумський національний аграрний університет, 2023

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	5
Contents of the course by topics	6
The concept “digital etiquette”	7
Virtual communication during distance and online learning	8
Basic rules of etiquette for teaching foreign language online	9
ZOOM etiquette	17
Social media etiquette	19
Email etiquette	22
Safety in media space and the basics of cyber security	27
Rules of safe behavior in the virtual world	31
References	32

INTRODUCTION

In the pandemic and post-pandemic society, information and communications technology (ICT) and various digital devices have become an integral part of life of every individual and modern generation of youth, who belong to the generation of centennials, as no one else reflects the trends of the times. Since digital technologies are increasing in number and in importance, it is necessary to apply them in the process of organizing and conducting educational classes.

The process of digitization of higher education affects the direction of foreign language teaching as well. In today's realities, a foreign language lecturer must have a good understanding not only of teaching methods, but also of technologies. Every year, various platforms for learning foreign languages, innovative and interactive tools are developed and effectively used in practice, which help students better learn the educational material. Considering the fact that the last three years of study mostly take place remotely, the role of these technologies in foreign language training of students is quite decisive.

In recent decades, there has been a rapid expansion of virtual communication, which has led to the development of a culture of virtual communication and the development of rules of behavior on the Internet. Learning how to conduct oneself online is essential to becoming a successful 21st century citizen. Life in the network has long become an important part of our lives. We communicate every day through messengers, social media and e-mail. Currently, the effectiveness of interpersonal communication requires adaptation to new conditions of virtual space, mastering new skills. Against the background of online communication, an important component of interaction appears as digital etiquette, which provides for the rules of communication in the digital space, communication without harm to oneself and others. In the conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, this issue has become even more urgent, so adaptation to new realities has brought the problem of digital etiquette to a new level. Digital etiquette is a new type of etiquette that defines the rules of behavioral culture in the digital environment of the Internet.

Contents of the course by topics

Media literacy in the context of communication and collaboration: interacting, sharing, collaborating through digital technologies; netiquette; managing digital identity.

Subtopics

1. How to communicate online. Virtual communication in the process of distance and online learning via Zoom, Google Meet, Viber, WhatsApp, Telegram.
2. Basic rules of etiquette for teaching foreign language online. Possibilities of Zoom service in foreign language teaching.
3. Rules of behavior during a video conference. Chat etiquette.
4. Social media etiquette. The use of social media in the process of target language teaching. Social media as a source of news and social interaction. Peculiarities of communication in social networks.
5. Email etiquette. Communication via email. Rules of writing emails.

Safety in media space and the basics of cyber security: protecting devices; protecting personal data and privacy; protecting health and well-being; different forms of cyber-bulling (trolling, slander, phishing, etc.) and counteracting to them.

Subtopics

1. The concept of a safe Internet.
2. Positive and negative factors of using the Internet.
3. Fundamentals of cyber security. Internet security.
4. Protection in the digital environment.
5. Rules of safe behavior in the virtual world.

What is Digital Etiquette?

Etiquette, the behavioral requirements per societal conventions and what is customary among others in a professional or casual setting.

Emotional intelligence is at the core of any etiquette system. No one is perfectly emotionally intelligent, of course. We all have little areas of doubt when it comes to our behavior. Whether online or in real life, etiquette rules aim to make one another feel as welcome and comfortable as possible.

Digital etiquette provides us with rules of behavior for using technology to interact with others. It is similar to everyday etiquette. When we are online it is really important that we treat people the way we would do ‘in real life’, by using respectful language, respecting other people’s privacy and by not excluding others.

Netiquette, a combination of *network* and *etiquette*, can be used interchangeably with the term digital etiquette.

According to Encyclopedia Britannica, netiquette is a set of “guidelines for courteous communication in the online environment.” Netiquette guidelines include rules for both social interaction and technical activities on the internet.

Digital etiquette sets standards for online conduct and how one should behaviour in a digital environment. In particular, it is important to establish rules for proper use of digital devices. Without proper digital etiquette, the digital world can become a hostile place of pretences, false comfort, and misinformed facts. This can sometimes lead to unfortunate events such as cyber bullying and online scamming.

Digital etiquette covers any online behavior. However, much of it can be organized into behaviors associated with the following:

- Online classes;
- Social media, particularly concerning the prevention of bullying and other abusive behavior;
- Email for both personal use and study;
- Protecting the privacy of personal information for one’s self and others;
- Information consumption and dissemination, particularly for news media.

Virtual communication during distance and online learning

Issues for Discussion:

- Comparison of online and in-person learning (Advantages and disadvantages).
- Basics and principles of online communication between participants of the educational process.
- Peculiarities of setting up online communications.

Digital technologies have become an integral part of teaching and learning a foreign language, helping to organize the educational process. Currently, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet are the most common platforms in Ukraine for conducting classes that provide the possibility of video conferencing.

Online communication means any communication made through a computer, computer system, computer network, telecommunication, telecommunications device, telecommunications service, information service, or other digital or electronic method of communication.

There are many free instant messengers available now which allow to communicate with friends with text, phone call, video, sharing of files, in group or not and keep contact with them even internationally. Interpersonal interactive communication is implemented by using synchronous tools, but remotely, via *Zoom, Google Meet, Viber, WhatsApp, Telegram*, etc. They make it possible to supplement learning management systems and implement not just the exchange of information, but the communicative interaction of partners in a foreign language, which is quite significant given the insufficient number of hours allocated in a non-linguistic institution of higher education for foreign language training of students.

More important factor for the effective organization of distance learning is careful planning of classes and a clear vision of the application of appropriate technologies in each specific case. However, in order not to overload the educational process, the lecturer should focus on a limited number of proven Internet tools that really work and contribute to productive educational activities.

Basic rules of etiquette for teaching foreign language online

Issues for Discussion:

- Rules of writing text messages.
- Digital etiquette during blackouts.
- Use of emojis in text messages.

Practical classes are held online by means of Zoom and Google Classroom software, which makes it possible to study in video conference mode. *Zoom platform* is used especially effectively by lecturers to conduct synchronous classes online. The platform offers free and fairly high-quality video and audio communication, provides the ability to communicate by means of short text messages. Various forms of oral and written communication between all participants of the educational process take part in Zoom conferences and chat rooms, providing either prepared or spontaneous interaction with the integrated use of ICT through the exchange of written, audio and video information; inviting guests (experts, foreign specialists, etc.), conducting students' surveys, interviews and their online broadcast.

There are the following benefits of Zoom platform:

- psychologically comfortable and contributed to the fostering of their oral communication and intercultural skills;
- students' acquaintance with online speech etiquette,
- fostering students' ability to hear and understand ideas of interlocutors; persuasion skills, argumentation of one's point of view, adequate response, predicting the response of interlocutors.

Among Zoom functions, lecturers most frequently use the Chat function, the Online Whiteboard function, the Screen Demonstration function, and the Breakout Rooms function. Using the "Screen Demonstration" function allows participants of the learning process to listen to audio materials, view video materials, presentations, perform interactive tasks, and operate text files in shared viewing mode.

The most popular element of this product among teachers is students' work organization function in Breakout Rooms. This option allows students to work in groups, for example, they can conduct dialogues. The lecturer is able to divide students into appropriate groups, with whom he can maintain an educational connection during the duration of the sessions. In addition, both the lecturer and students have the opportunity to use auxiliary tools during video communication: presentations (created by means of such graphic tools as Microsoft Power Point, Google Presentations, Google Slides, etc.), audio and video materials, various Internet resources.

Foreign language teachers also use such an online platform as *Google Classroom*. The system is easy to use, has all the necessary functionality for the effective organization of the educational environment, allows to place learning materials from a local or cloud drive, contains good functionality for writing and checking written assignments. Although the system does not have a built-in tool for conducting online meetings, lecturers can also use a free tool for organizing conferences with the ability to display the speaker's screen and a communication tool called Google Meet. However, all the opportunities provided by Google Classroom will be effective only when the lecturer has thought through, prepared materials, presentations, audio recordings, exercises, etc.

Other communication services that are actively used in distance learning of a foreign language are Viber and Telegram. With the help of these messengers, teachers can quickly send homework in the form of both text files and multimedia files, as well as links to certain Internet resources. In addition, it is convenient to correspond with students and provide them with the necessary consultations and clarifications by creating a chat for this purpose.

Considering messengers as a learning environment in the educational process, we note that they are not only a program or web service for quick exchange of messages of various formats. Most messengers allow voice and video conferences.

There are a lot of such programs now, and the most popular of them are Viber, WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Telegram.

Let's analyze some features of the most popular messengers.

For example, Viber offers the largest number of emojis, stickers and chat backgrounds; provides the ability to create control surveys with the choice of the correct answer, open chats and simultaneous connection with many mobile devices.

In Internet communication, forms of communication do not have rigid frameworks, the use of emoticons, memes, expressions from different languages is allowed. All this helps to remove psychological barriers in communicating in a foreign language.

The main function of the messenger is to transmit information in the most comprehensive form using text.

Rules of etiquette

You need to follow the same rules and standards of behavior that you follow in real life:

- The privacy of others should be respected.
- You should not write messages at night, especially if it is something minor and non-urgent (messages will wake up the addressee, because not everyone turns off notifications at night). In addition, some messengers have a delayed message or "send without sound" function.
- You should value other people's time and traffic: don't force anyone to waste it.
- It is necessary to archive large files, do not record meaningless voice messages and do not write many messages with one word.
- Messages in the messenger should be answered by the end of the day, because the purpose of creating these applications is to get closer to live communication. Therefore, the answer in a month will definitely be inappropriate and irrelevant.

Discussion: Digital etiquette during blackouts

We all communicate online in chats and messengers every day. But how have your skills and habits changed in digital communication?

During power outages, digital etiquette can become more important than ever. We'll try to figure out how to be the most efficient, polite and useful to our interlocutors.

- ✓ Be aware of limited available resources and use them sparingly. Write shorter messages, avoid unnecessary communication, do not send voice and video messages, pay attention to the size of the file you are transferring. All these steps will help save network traffic.
- ✓ Use secure communication methods whenever possible to protect sensitive information.
- ✓ Please be aware that there may be communication interruptions, so please be patient if messages are delayed or do not go through.
- ✓ It is important to observe information hygiene and check information before sharing it. Misinformation can be damaging and create unnecessary panic.
- ✓ Be respectful and considerate when dealing with others, even in high-stress situations.
- ✓ If you have an unstable connection during an online meeting, you can try turning off the camera.
- ✓ Do not send short phrases and sentences in separate messages. It will be much more convenient for a person to receive all the information in one structured message. Especially if there are interruptions in communication. Describe everything at once, to the point.
- ✓ If it is a longer message, try to divide it into points, questions, highlight the important ones. Especially since many messengers allow you to use bold and italics for convenience.

A separate aspect of remote communication in messengers is its communicative features, namely:

- expressiveness (selecting in any way one or another content from a number of other transmitted contents). This is usually implemented by repeating punctuation marks "!!!", ")))";
- dialogicity (use of exclamatory sentences, imperative);
- oral-written nature of the language (use of emojis, stickers, abbreviations, simplified transcription to save time and effort).

Use of emojis

Gestures, body movements, facial expressions accompany, strengthen, specify, add nuances, and sometimes replace verbal means of communication. Emojis perform similar functions in written interactive communication, they are part of the text like punctuation marks and are usually found at the end of a sentence.

With the help of emojis, it is possible to express not only emotions, but also thousands of other concepts. They are used instead of or to reinforce the meaning of a word, which can be a noun, verb or adjective. They can personify not only objects, people or animals, but also gestures and facial expressions.

There are three *basic functions of emoji for learning a foreign language*: substitution (use instead of a word), duplication (strengthening of emotional meaning), content creation (several signs together can carry a certain meaning).

There are practical ways to use emojis in class with students – lexical workshop, learning about cultural traditions and text creation

We will give exercises to practice the skills of using emojis.

1. During the introduction of new vocabulary, students are offered a list of words and a number of emojis of a certain topic. Students have to combine pictographic and linguistic components.

Working in pairs on a text where lexical items are omitted, one student has a list of words, the other has a set of emojis. They have to fill in the blanks and sound out or write the complete text.

The samples of exercises for learning new vocabulary depend on the level of students and the technical capabilities of phones. The formation of a stable association “emoji – lexical unit” occurs after a 15-20 second demonstration of the word, transcription and corresponding emoji on a computer screen or interactive whiteboard with 3-4 repetitions.

Repetition of learned vocabulary can be carried out through a team competition, when a graphic list of foreign language vocabulary on a certain topic is provided on the board, and the team that reproduces the emojis of these concepts the fastest on their mobile phones wins. There are also tasks for consolidating new material – replacing individual words with emojis and vice versa, searching for correspondences, emoji crosswords and flash cards.

2. The second function of using emoji is related to *the culture of the country* which language the students are studying. Among the forms of work, interactive group forms have advantages, when students conduct exploratory cultural research. Definitions of gestural features of a foreign language, which are reflected in emojis, are especially useful.

For example, two folded hands 🙏 may mean religious concepts in the East, but “thank you” or “please” in Japan. A white flower means homework for Japanese students; we are used to the gesture – thumb raised up 👍 – to be understood as positive: “Great!” “Super!”, but in some countries this gesture has an offensive meaning.

3. The function of text creation – the use of emoji under this condition contributes to the modernization of communication and the discovery of new facets of language units. Practices which we can offer aim to reveal the creative potential of those who study. The student chooses 6 emojis: three of an emotional nature, and three should denote an object. First, he introduces each character into the situation, and then makes up a little story using all six. Students exchange their stories, answer each other's questions, and the teacher acts as a consultant. A group exercise to create a continuation of a regular text with several emojis at the end is promising for the student audience.

We offer the following motivational exercises:

- choose emoji verbs in such a way that the partner guesses the verb (for example, eyes – “to see”, etc.);
- team game – the teacher provides a number of emojis so that students make up a story that is either as funny as possible or as close to the original one as possible (for example, “How I planted a tree”);
- make sentences with emojis instead of words;
- replace images with words;
- compilation of cards for decoding;
- choosing emojis at random and using them in written messages;
- analyzing the meaning of a phrase with different emojis at the end;
- watching the video “Emoji Emotions”

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6B0NBVT6VP4>

To overcome the difficulties of communication in messengers, it is necessary to be able to correctly convey and interpret information in text format, to use emojis correctly, to take into account the factors that affect this type of communication, to maintain “transparency” – to be active and open.

Such out-of-class text communication has not only practical purposes, but also psychological ones, since informal communication makes it possible to relieve some tension in communication between students and teachers or between students in general. In these Viber- or Telegram-chats, to create a positive emotional mood, students can share cognitive Internet discoveries, and the teacher can also send links to high-quality and new educational materials.

For instance, you can share current news, jokes, video clips, fragments from TV series, feature and documentary films, TV programs, video blogs that are relevant to the conversational topic being studied, that is, those Internet resources which there is not enough time to study in the class and that have a positive effect in strengthening motivation to learn a foreign language.

Zoom etiquette

Issue for Discussion:

- Rules of behavior during a video conference

Video conferencing has become a unique technology for distance learning and communication with the effect of presence. This technology provides simultaneous two-way transmission, processing, transformation and presentation of interactive information at a distance in real time applying digital devices. Practical classes are mainly carried out by foreign language lecturers by means of Zoom, which provides the opportunity to conduct foreign language classes in video format and online mode. Due to a wide range of built-in functions, Zoom demonstrates high efficiency in the implementation of a foreign language learning process.

The specificity of conducting video conferences is to establish contact with participants in several ways:

- in writing (in chat);
- visually, using a web camera;
- technically, which confirms the presence of an Internet connection;
- acoustically (voice, using a microphone).

To discuss *Rules of behavior during a video conference* students can be offered to watch the video “Video conference etiquette” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k6aN4j6YzKM>

Rules of interaction are determined and announced at the beginning of the conference, guided by the principle of courtesy and taking into account the specifics of online communication. Such rules, in particular, are:

- ✓ keep the camera on and the microphones off ;
- ✓ turn on the microphone only when you speak;
- ✓ be virtually present;
- ✓ have virtual patience;
- ✓ to say something or ask a question, you need to raise your hand by clicking on the corresponding icon .

Applying the chat helps maintain the principle of civility. Chat is used for the purpose of maintaining contact with the entire audience, bringing communication closer to a live one. It allows you to communicate both with the whole group and with an individual student. The private chat feature on Zoom allows a lecturer to send instructions or corrections directly to students. In the chat, you can report technical problems if they arise (unstable Internet connection, microphone or camera failure, problems with presentation, etc.). According to the rules of etiquette, you shouldn't write the text in the chat in all capital letters, because typing in all capital letters is referred to as “screaming” or “shouting”.

A lecturer can also use this to give feedback or grammar notes to individual students in real time, during lessons. Some students are not quite confident to ask in spoken way, so they use this feature. It also allows a lecturer to give students individual praise anonymously, which is great for motivation. The video conferencing feature (private and group) enables lecturers to communicate directly with students and monitor important evaluation aspects of speaking skills, such as word choice, pronunciation accuracy, grammar, comprehension, fluency, and intonation accuracy.

Social media etiquette

Issues for Discussion:

- Digital etiquette in wartime: Social media do's and don'ts.
- Fake social media profiles.

Social media is a powerful communication tool, in the space of which users have the opportunity to create groups, exchange information (text messages, photo, video, audio materials, links to certain sources), work together on projects, etc.

In pedagogy, social networks are considered as “a virtual platform that provides support, creation, development, display and organization of social contacts with its means of communication, in particular, data exchange between users and necessarily involves the prior creation of an account”; “an interactive, multi-user website, the content of which is filled by the network participants themselves, an automated social environment that allows communication between a group of users united by a common interest”.

The purpose of social media is not limited in entertainment function. The process of information exchange is two-way, as users both transmit information (perform the function of a communicator) and receive it (are recipients). Inclusion in the discussion of a certain circle of events, clarifying the point of view of other users forces one to clearly formulate one's own position, which ultimately contributes to the self-identity of the individual. Since individual users also post the results of their work (paintings, drawings, poetic works, videos, etc.) on the networks, this contributes to their self-realization and encourages self-development.

Among the didactic advantages of using social networks and messengers, there are the following:

- exchange of information, communication between groups that are at a distance;
- realization of creative potential;
- reading and commenting on news, various information, materials; discussion of issues and topics;

- publishing and receiving information about the schedule of classes, training, tasks, etc.;
- a significant range of services, a variety of forms of communication, exchange of interesting and useful links to other resources;
- the possibility of group activity, joint planning and filling of educational content;
- constant interaction of the student and teacher in the network at a time convenient for them and the organization of individual work with each student;
- availability of a mobile version of pages, etc.

There are some speaking tasks for students:

Conversational cards

What social media do you use?

What are the advantages of social media?

What do you do on social media?

Why do you share photos?

Do you worry that your teachers might read your posts?

Have you ever posted something that you regret?

Discussion: Digital etiquette in wartime: Social media do's and don'ts.

Now digital etiquette has fundamentally changed. Even a small blog has a certain circle of readers on whom it has influence. Therefore, it is important to know what to write about and what information to avoid.

You can publish:

- positive news and reports from the front;
- verified fees;
- results of volunteer work;
- inspections of institutions that resumed their work or did not stop it;
- advice on improving emotional, psychological and physical condition;
- stories about the heroism of Ukrainians;

- memes and funny stories.

In the publication of news and meetings, the main thing is to check the durability and truthfulness of the information. Whoever spreads the post in one way or another is responsible for the consequences. Therefore, you should make sure that the information will not harm users.

What should be avoided?

It is not allowed to publish information about the movement and location of equipment and soldiers of the armed forces of Ukraine. It is also strictly forbidden to provide information about shelling, the provision of weapons and their transportation. You shouldn't publish photos from parties on the day of the tragedy or mass shootings. You shouldn't also make posts about what is bad. Today you have to be very careful in social networks. Do not turn the feed into a negative news report.

Discussion: Fake social media profiles.

NFT Fraud Scheme – “Fake Social Media Profiles”. Often these are copies of real accounts with minor changes.

Therefore, it is worth paying attention to new profiles in social media, sometimes one letter in the nickname makes it clear that the account is fraudulent.

At the same time, bots that encourage users to respond to messages or scammers posing as technical support use social media to lure users with data to access crypto wallets.

Moreover, attackers may try to contact users by sending messages under the pretense of chatting or getting advice.

Typical signs of their schemes will help identify scammers: in particular, the number of subscribers, publications, as well as the lack of genuine content in the account.

Email etiquette

Issues for Discussion:

- Email structure
- Formal and informal emails
- Language and tone of the email

Email is a very common mode of communication at university, in the workplace and socially. It's important to get the tone and style of your email right, as this will help you make a good impression and hopefully get the response you're looking for. Having a good email etiquette makes it more likely that people will respond positively to your emails. It shows people that you are professional and polite, and makes it less likely to cause misunderstandings.

There are some tips for teaching email etiquette

1. Review purpose

The first aspect of teaching email etiquette is explaining its purpose versus other forms of written communication. Cover the difference in purpose between an email and a text message. As students are so familiar with text messaging, they can start their comparison with what they know. Then, they can move into the differences with email. Ultimately, a discussion in formality is important. Therefore, discussing scenarios could be a great way to show when a text message makes sense versus when a situation calls for a more formal email.

2. Use an exemplary example

Considering this discussion in formality, students next can benefit from seeing an example of what an effective email looks like. Since the formatting is different from both an essay and text message, students need to learn the block formatting.

Still, it's not just about formatting. Analyzing the content of an exemplary example can be a great way to emphasize the formality of an email. So, use an example that would be relevant to students' email needs. For example, a thank you email to a teacher or an email to a college admissions' representative.

Standard email etiquette

There are several things to consider when showing email etiquette.

Email address

Your email address should appear professional. It should convey your name so the recipient knows who is sending the email, as demonstrated in the example below.

Good email address example

- john.smith@gmail.com
- jane_brown@gmail.com

Subject line

You should always include a subject line that explains exactly to the recipient what the email is addressing. A subject line should be clear and direct, as demonstrated in the example below.

Line examples

- Subject: Questions on Assignment 1
- Subject: Meeting date changes

Greeting

It is basic courtesy to address the recipient at the start of the email rather than jumping straight into the body of the email. If you do not know the name of the person you are emailing, begin your email with a simple 'Hello'. Examples of how to address recipients can be seen below.

How to start a formal email? At the beginning of your email, greet a person by name. Depending on the level of formality, your salutations may vary from a simple "Hi" to an official "Dear Mr./Ms./Dr./Professor..." For the most formal occasions, use a colon instead of a comma after the salutation. For example, "Dear Ms. Smith:"

Here are some email greeting examples:

Hello [Name],

Dear [Name],

Dear Mr./Ms./Dr./Professor [Last name],

Greetings,

Always do your best to find out the recipient's name to address them in your email. If your research wasn't successful, use a generic salutation like "Greetings."

Examples

- Dear Ms/Mrs/Mr/Dr Franklin,
- Hi James

Email body

Here's how to do it:

- Always devote one email to one topic. For example, you may need your colleague to review your quarterly report and discuss the hiring strategy for your department. This is too much information for a single email! It's better to send two separate messages on each subject, making it easy for a person to answer. This way, you're more likely to get a fast reply.
- Explain what you're writing about. If you're emailing a stranger, briefly introduce yourself and then go straight to the point. State the purpose of your email clearly so a person can understand why you're emailing them and how they can help. For example:

I would like to invite you to speak at our annual developer conference.

I'm running a YouTube blog about cats, and we'd love to feature your brand in our next video.

I've been using your service for a while, and I would like to report an issue I've recently encountered.

- Value the reader's time. Provide a recipient with any additional information they need to reply. At the same time, try to keep your email short and simple and don't overload it with extra details. Remember that email isn't the best place for a lengthy discussion.
- Make your email easy to read. Break your message into paragraphs and take advantage of headings and lists. Where it's appropriate, emphasize the key

information with bold or *italics*, just don't overdo it. Your goal is to make your email as structured and easy to skim as possible.

Formal email closing

The formal email closing tells a recipient what's next. If you want them to do something, include a clear and specific call to action. If you're just wrapping up the discussion you've previously had, end your email on a friendly note to show a reader you're willing to keep in touch with them.

Here's how to end a formal email:

Please let me know by Friday, August 15th if you'd like to speak at the conference.

It would be great to jump into a quick call tomorrow to discuss our collaboration.

Thank you for help and feedback. Let's keep in touch!

Signature

Here are the polite phrases you can use to sign off your email:

Sincerely,

Best regards,

Yours truly,

Respectfully,

Kind regards,

Thanks again,

Language and tone

Keep your writing simple, clear and direct to avoid the risk of ambiguity. The sentences should be short and complete and never use SMS language like you would when text messaging your friends like 'btw' for by the way, 'u' for you or 'tmrw' for tomorrow.

Be mindful of your tone of voice in the email as it can be misconstrued without the context that comes from vocal cues and facial expressions in face-to-face

situations. In addition, avoid using explicitly negative words such as ‘failure’, ‘wrong’ or ‘neglected’ and always end with a ‘please’ and ‘thank you’

3. Teach Technical Uses (and Mistakes)

The most important aspects of teaching email etiquette is understanding how to send an email appropriately. With to, carbon copy, blind carbon, forward, reply, and reply all options, email can be quite confusing (and even embarrassing if done wrong). Explaining how each of these technical elements works is vital to set up students for success in the real world.

4. Put it into practice

One of the ways to make email etiquette stick is having students put what they learned into practice. First, give them a real-world scenario, something they’d encounter in the near future. This ensures that they understand the purpose and format. Then, the next step requires that they actually send an email to practice the technical parts. Use fun and engaging scenarios, and have them email for practice. One tip is to have them work in groups, so you’re not overwhelmed with even more emails!

Work in groups: writing email

- ✓ Your mom and dad asked you to email your aunt an apology. Write an email to your aunt apologizing for missing Sunday dinner at her house. Blind copy your mom and dad, so they know you sent it.
- ✓ You received an email from a college coach asking for your high school transcripts. Reply to the email by attaching the transcript and copy your high school guidance counselor.
- ✓ You are working with a group on a project, and you have a question for your teacher. Email your teacher to ask the question. Copy all of your group members so they can be in the loop.

Safety in media space and the basics of cyber security

Issues for Discussion

- Private and personal information
- Nothing online is completely private

The concept of a safe Internet

During the class, students receive information about common types of threats in the virtual space:

1) threats related to personal safety:

- ✓ familiarization with pornographic materials, profanity, information of a suicidal nature, racist, hateful or sectarian content;
- ✓ threat of receiving unreliable or false information;
- ✓ formation of addiction (gaming, computer, Internet);
- ✓ communication with dangerous people (perverts, swindlers, swindlers);
- ✓ involvement in illegal actions (hacking, violation of the rights and freedoms of others).

2) threats affecting the safety of other persons;

- ✓ materials, the existence and use of which may be a cause of encroachment on the safety of others;
- ✓ knowingly and unknowingly misleading others;
- ✓ committing illegal actions;
- ✓ cyberbullying – deliberate bullying and humiliation, primarily of peers.

3) threats related to the danger of leaking personal information:

- ✓ disclosure of personal and confidential information (surnames, first names, contacts, secret credit card data, phone numbers).
- ✓ the threat of infecting a personal computer with viruses of various categories.
- ✓ the danger of downloading programs with malicious functions.

It should be noted, that an important tool against the threat of personal data leakage is a proper password. It is necessary to inform students about the signs of a dangerous password:

1. One of your passwords is 123456, 111111, admin, etc.
2. Your password is your first name, last name, phone number, and the name of your hometown.
3. The password consists of only letters or numbers and contains less than five characters.
4. When coming up with a password, you choose words from the dictionary, remember the names of popular artists or groups.
5. Use of identical or adjacent symbols. For example, 222222 or xcvbnm.
6. You type Ukrainian words in English layout.

The signs of a secure password:

1. It consists of more than eight characters.
2. The password contains mixed letters and numbers, lower and upper case and other characters (for example, Ju25lix/93aHl, SPR45kg78#1, etc.).
3. Lack of a clear connection of the password with you and your relatives. The password, at first glance, consists of meaningless words, but you know the logic of its formation (so that you remember it).
4. You use both Cyrillic and Latin letters in its creation.
5. The words in the password are written with errors, some letters are mixed up or replaced.
6. You should always complete actions on the Internet related to entering a password.
7. Separate passwords for different accounts and sites.
8. Regular password change.

There are some tasks for students to be done:

1. Read the following statements. Choose if it's personal or private information.

My first full name.

My favorite food.

My university address.

Publish photos of my pets.

My home address.

A photo of myself.

My birthday date.

My favorite computer games.

2. Write an example of a secure password. Explain your choice.

Students also receive information about dangerous aspects of communication on the Internet.

Trolling – activity on the Internet, which consists in the publication of provocative messages, the purpose of which may be to attract attention, in response to flood, flame, lulz, offtopics, conflicts, etc.

Trolling can be seen as harassment, but it has two main differences:

- 1) it is based on a conscious attitude, and its main goal is to provoke the public to flood and lulz;
- 2) trolling is aimed at an indefinite number of the public, while in bullying the main goal is to humiliate a certain person.

The way to identify a troll: manner of communication, often an empty account, naming names of celebrities, lack of private information, real friends, etc.

The way to deal with trolling: Ignore it.

Griffing is a form of trolling in online games. Griffer in games creates conflict situations with the aim of harming other players. Griffers, like trolls, try to do everything in order to successfully provoke as many people as possible into conflicts and quarrels. The way to fight: ignore, complain to the server administrator.

Phishing is a type of fraud, the purpose of which is to lure the personal data of customers of online auctions, money transfer or exchange services, and online stores from gullible or inattentive network users. Fraudsters use all kinds of manipulations, which most often force users to reveal confidential data on their own, for example, by sending e-mails with offers to confirm account registration, which contain links to a website on the Internet, the appearance of which completely copies the design of well-known resources.

Phishing is a telephone fraud associated with luring bank card details or other confidential information, coercion to transfer funds to the thieves' card.

Smishing (it is from words "SMS" and "phishing") is a type of phishing via SMS. Fraudsters send the victim an SMS containing a link to a phishing website and a motivational message to log in to the site. An "evil twin" attack is a type of phishing common in wireless computer networks. The fraudster creates a copy of a wireless access point that is within the user's reception radius, thereby replacing the original access point with a duplicate to which the user connects, opening the attacker's opportunity to access confidential information.

Methods of struggle: do not open mail from unknown addressees; do not download programs from unfamiliar sites; do not trust calls asking for confidential information.

There are some speaking tasks for students:

Conversational cards

What kind of information is your profile?

Is your privacy important to you? Why?

What is personal data for you?

Whatever you put online is permanent. How do you feel about this?

Have you ever been bullied online?

Have you ever seen or heard of somebody being bullied online?

Rules of safe behavior in the virtual world

How to protect yourself in cyberspace?

Remember: When you post information on the Internet, you lose control over it. Deleting the material and its copies is practically impossible.

Check: You should know exactly to whom you provide information, as well as how and for what purpose it will be used. Think: Should you post information if you don't know how it will be used and whether it will harm you or your loved ones?

Reminder about safe behavior and communication on the Internet:

1. Don't give your passwords to anyone, keep them safe.
2. Do not provide personal information by mail or in chats without an urgent need.
3. Do not respond to obscene and rude comments addressed to you.
4. Notify loved ones about situations on the Internet that worry you (threats, files with certain content, offers).
5. Refuse meetings with random people you met online.
6. Do not share your photos with strangers, even if you trust them.
7. Do not disclose information about bank cards (card number, expiration date, and secret code).
8. Do not post photos of tickets that show a barcode or QR code.
9. Do not download or install unknown programs from links, even if they were given by friends.
10. When installing verified programs, make sure that no unwanted programs are added to your computer.
11. Do not view information on unknown links (friends who share them may not be aware of the threat).
12. Do not open spam emails, they may contain viruses.

Discussion in groups: Explain the statement "Nothing online is completely private".

REFERENCES

1. Андрійченко, Ж. О., Близнюк, Т. П., & Майстренко, В. О. (2021). Digital етикет та комунікації: тенденції та вимоги сьогодення. *Економіка та суспільство*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2021-34-24>
2. Bilotserkovets, M., Fomenko, T., Gubina, O., Klochkova, T., Lytvynko, O., Boichenko, M., & Lazareva, O. (2021). Fostering Media Literacy Skills in the EFL Virtual Classroom: A Case Study in the COVID-19 Lockdown Period. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(2), 251-269. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.2.14>
3. Білоцерковець, М., Фоменко, Т., & Лущик, Ю. (2023). Основні практики медіаграмотності ЄС для формування критичного мислення студентів у контексті навчання іноземної мови: навчальна програма. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7633246>
4. Destianingsih, A., & Satria, A. (2020). Investigating students' needs for effective English online learning during Covid-19 for polbeng students. *ELT-Lectura: Studies and Perspectives in English Language Teaching*, 7(2), 147-153. <https://doi.org/10.31849/elt-lectura.v7i2.4657>
5. Economidou-Kogetsidis, M. (2015). Teaching email politeness in the EFL/ESL classroom. *ELT Journal*, 69(4), 415-424.
6. Emoji Emotions. iJustine: YouTube. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c2BcR39AtxE>
7. Grajek, S. (2016, December 12). The Digitization Of Higher Education: Charting the course. Educause Review. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2016/12/thedigitization-of-higher-education-chartingthe-course>
8. Заблоцький, Ю. (2021). Використання інтернет-інструментів в умовах дистанційного навчання для вивчення іноземної мови. *Наукові записки Національного університету "Острозька академія": серія "Філологічна"*, 11(79), 3-7. [https://doi.org/10.25264/2519-2558-2021-11\(79\)-3-7](https://doi.org/10.25264/2519-2558-2021-11(79)-3-7)

9. Jones, L. (2019). Three Innovative Approaches to Integrating Emoji into Your Language Lessons. *FLTMAG.com*. Retrieved from: <https://fltmag.com/integrating-emoji-into-your-language-lessons/>
10. Jonker, N. (2021, June 29). Proper Emoji Etiquette: When to Use (or Not Use) Them. *Social media*. <https://www.makeuseof.com/emoji-etiquette-when-to-use-them/>
11. Конюкова, І. Я., & Сидоровська, Є. А. (2021). Цифровий етикет комунікативної культури XXI століття. *Вісник Національної академії керівних кадрів культури і мистецтв: наук. журнал*, 1, 26-30. <https://doi.org/10.32461/2226-3209.1.2021.229542>
12. Кречотень, О. В., & Березняк, О. П. (2020). Дидактичні можливості використання емодзі в курсі іноземної мови нелінгвістичного університету. *Педагогіка формування творчої особистості у вищій і загальноосвітній школах*, 70(2). 191-195. <https://doi.org/10.32840/1992-5786.2020.70-2.36>
13. Krzl, N. (2020, December 28). 10 Rules of Etiquette for Teaching English Online. *BridgeUniverse*. <https://bridge.edu/tefl/blog/rules-of-etiquette-teaching-english-online/>
14. Майстренко, О., Андрійченко, Ж., & Близнюк, Т. (2022). Етика комунікації працівників у соціальних мережах та її вплив на імідж компанії. *Економіка та суспільство*, 38. <https://doi.org/10.32782/2524-0072/2022-38-20>
15. Menggo, S. (2021). Perception and barrier on using Zoom in speaking class during COVID-19 pandemic. *The First International Conference on Humanities, Education, Language and Culture*. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.30-7-2021.2313619>
16. Методика інтеграції в проєкті «Вивчай та розрізняй: інфомедійна грамотність»: збірник матеріалів / Редкол.: В. Ф. Іванов (голов. ред.) [та ін.]. Київ: Академія української преси, IREX, Центр вільної преси, 2022. 160 с.
17. Nafisatul Mu'awanah, Sumardi, & Suparno (2021). Using Zoom to Support English Learning during Covid-19 Pandemic: Strengths and Challenges. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Dasar* 5(2), 222-230. <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/JISD/index>

18. Слюсаренко, Н., & Сотер, М. (2022). Цифровізація іншомовної підготовки у закладах вищої освіти України. *Людинознавчі студії. Серія «Педагогіка»*, 14(46), 48-55. <https://doi.org/10.24919/2413-2039.13/46.7>
19. Soler-Costa, R., Lafarga-Ostáriz, P., Mauri-Medrano, M., & Moreno-Guerrero, A. J. (2021). Netiquette: ethic, education, and behavior on internet – a systematic literature review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(3), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031212>
20. Suardi, M. (2020). The effectiveness of using the Zoom Cloud Meetings application in the learning process. *Proceeding of The International Conference on Science and Advanced Technology (ICSAT) (pp. 591-602)*. <https://ojs.unm.ac.id/icsat/article/view/17730/9651>
21. Sung-Chul, L., Jaeyoon, S., Eun-Young, K., Seongho, P., & Juho, K. (2020). The relationship between online activities, netiquette and cyberbullying. *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. Children and youth services review*, (101), 74-81. <http://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376609>
22. For tips for teaching your students appropriate email etiquette (2022, March 1). *JENNARCOPPER.COM*. <http://jennacopper.com/email-etiquette/>
23. Харчук, Л. Н. (2020). Мережевий мовленнєвий етикет в умовах сучасної комунікації. *Інформація, комунікація, суспільство*, 9, 128-129. <http://ena.lp.edu.ua:8080/handle/ntb/52767>
24. How to Write a Formal Email. <https://sparkmailapp.com/formal-email-template>
25. Цифровий етикет у період блекаутів. <https://insa.com.ua/blog/tsyfrovyyj-etyket-v-period-blekautiv/>
26. Черних, О. О. (2020). *Онлайн: навчально-методичний посібник*. Київ: ВАІТЕ. 108 с.
27. Як і про що писати в соцмережах в умовах війни. <https://kropyvnytskyi.one/uk/articles/yak-i-pro-shho-pysaty-v-soczmerezhah-v-umovah-vijny-3851>

**DIGITAL ETIQUETTE:
PRINCIPLES OF SPEAKING
AND BEHAVIOUR**

**Методичні вказівки щодо
проведення практичних занять**

Суми, РВВ, Сумський національний аграрний університет,
вул.Г.Кондратьєва,160

Підписано до друку:

Формат А5: Гарнітура Times New Roman

Тираж: 100 примірників Замовлення _____ Ум. друк. арк.
